

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D6.7 Electronic newsletter – Second Release

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Executive Summary

Youthmakers Hub, with the contribution of all partners, has produced the second newsletter; more will follow, one every semester. The newsletter was circulated in an electronic format to the interested public through the Mailchimp platform, and it was also uploaded to the official project webpage (<https://africoneu.eu/newsletter/>). The second newsletter of the project was released and sent on 21st January 2022. A database with e-mails has been developed during the last months with all people subscribed to our newsletter. 259 people received the newsletter. Four main categories have been included in the newsletter: About the project, Opportunities & News, Completed AfriConEU activities, Coming-up Online Workshop.

The issue published illustrated the achievements reached during the reported period, both in terms of projects developments as well as peripheral activities, such as participation in external events. Given the importance of the newsletter, concise, clear and simple sentences are important to spark and sustain interest in readers on the project.

[AfriConEU Newsletter #2 | January 2022](#)

AfriConEU Newsletter #2 | January 2022

Welcome to our second newsletter! We're glad you're here.
Twice a year, we inform you about the Project's progress.

Let's see the AfriConEU updates from the last 6 months.
If you missed our first newsletter, have a look [here](#).

About the project

This is AfriConEU

AfriConEU is an [Horizon 2020](#) project aspiring to create the first trans-Continental Networking Academy to support African and European Digital Innovation Hubs in capacity building, knowledge sharing, networking, joint projects, and venture development.

Here you can [read more about the project](#) or [meet the consortium](#).

Opportunities & News

Training Resources, Events & Job Opportunities

AfriConEU spreads the word about the latest opportunities, tools, and resources for individuals and DIHs within the African-European digital innovation ecosystem. To facilitate the access with a few clicks, we have added three new sections to our website: Training Resources, Events, and Job Opportunities.

The first includes high-quality online courses, webinars, and educational material. The second includes a repository with opportunities, including events, conferences, training seminars, and webinars relevant for digital innovation hubs, entrepreneurs, tech-hubs and startups in both Africa and Europe. The third is dedicated to vacancies for experts interested in finding a job. Check all our [Training Resources](#), [Events](#), and [Job Opportunities](#).

Join the AfriConEU Community of Practice

Do you have an opportunity for our Online Community? Do you have exciting Training Seminars and are looking for participants? Or are you simply looking for an opportunity provided by professionals in the field? Either way, our Online Community of Practice awaits you! You can offer your opportunities [here](#), or easily look for opportunities [here](#).

AfriConEU in the Press

During the last months, the development of the project has gained even more international recognition from several media related to innovation and entrepreneurship both in Africa and in Europe, including Tech Nova, Ameyaw Debrah, and startup.gr among others. See [AfriConEU in the media](#).

Completed AfriConEU Activities

AfriConEU Roundtable discussions: Challenges & Opportunities for EU-Africa Partnerships development

Outbox, from our Consortium, has hosted a series of interactive roundtable discussions. The goal was to highlight the necessity of networking and knowledge sharing, the strengthening of skills, and finding ways to overcome challenges and seize opportunities in the African digital innovation ecosystem.

AfriConEU Roundtable #1 | September 17th, 2021

“Improving access to funding for African DIHs & early-stage start-ups”

The first session was a start for a genuine dialogue upon the needs, problems, and opportunities for African DIHs & start-ups in Africa and Europe highlighting the importance of innovation as the point of differentiation and success of an idea. → [Read more](#)

AfriConEU Roundtable #2 | September 24th, 2021

“Knowledge exchange between DIHs in Africa and Europe”

The second discussion was focused on the different challenges DIHs/start-ups have to face in the two continents while paving the way to their use as tools for development. → [Read more](#)

AfriConEU Roundtable #3 | October 1st, 2021

“How might we improve access to markets for African and European start-ups?”

The last session of the roundtables brought Africa and Europe closer by sharing knowledge and experience on the digital innovation market and the policies regarding the DIHs and the start-up ecosystems. → [Read more](#)

Coming up: Online Workshop

The poster is split into two vertical panels. The left panel is yellow and contains the AfriConEU logo (a network of nodes forming an African continent) at the top and the Porto Business School logo (with 'University of Porto' in smaller text below) at the bottom. The right panel is dark blue and contains the text: '3rd February at 10:30 CET', 'DEVELOPMENT OF THE TRANS-CONTINENTAL PARTNERSHIPS' in large yellow letters, and 'FULL ONLINE' at the bottom.

Workshop: Development of the Trans-Continental Partnerships

We invite you to join us at this participative online workshop hosted by [Porto Business School](#), from our Consortium, aiming to discuss and co-design a programme focused on Africa-Europe partnerships in the innovation ecosystem, particularly among DIHs. The workshop will take place on the 3rd of February 2022 at 10:30 CET. Read more about the event [here](#), or register below.

[Register now](#)